

Teaching listening as a type of speech activity

Turaeva Shahida Egamberdievna
Karshi Engineering and Economic Institute

Annotation. The article analyzes the issue of working with text at the initial, intermediate, and advanced stages of studying Russian as a foreign language. The relevance of the article is determined by the possible application of the research results to solve significant scientific and practical problems.

Key words: speech motor analyzer, phonetic exercises, phonemic hearing, long-term memory, listening difficulties, listening training, probabilistic forecasting.

Listening is an oral receptive type of speech activity, the process of perceiving and understanding spoken speech, accompanied by complex mental activity and intense memory work. Mechanisms of listening The process of learning this type of speech activity is associated with the formation of the most important psychophysiological mechanisms. There is a strong connection between auditory and articulatory skills. When speech is perceived by ear, internal pronunciation occurs. The significance of internally speaking what is heard is very great.

Perceiving speech, the listener, using a speech motor analyzer, converts sound images into articulatory ones. Correct “voicing” of words “to oneself” is possible if the listener has clear pronunciation skills. Therefore, listening should be preceded by speech and phonetic exercises, singing, and imitation. Learning to listen begins with the formation of phonemic and intonation hearing. Clear pronunciation skills are one of the conditions that facilitate the perception process.

To develop speech hearing, there are various types of exercises: “Listen and repeat..”, and imitation exercises can be at the level of words, sentences, phrases. Exercises for isolating sounds, syllables, phrases, semantic parts in an isolated or connected text are useful for the development of speech hearing. Probabilistic forecasting plays an important role in developing listening skills. The language experience that students already have contributes to the fact that they can, after hearing part of a word, sentence or message, predict its end.

Probabilistic forecasting manifests itself at all levels of language - from syllable to text. Understanding words depends on the development of phonemic hearing,

knowledge of the laws of word formation and word compatibility, and the ability to relate the meanings of words to the context. Finally, to understand a sentence, students must retain in memory the entire sound sequence of words that make up the sentence. The shorter it is, the easier it is to remember. This is due to the activity of short-term and long-term memory. Psychologists have found that the capacity of short-term memory is limited, therefore, when teaching listening at the initial stage, it is recommended to use sentences whose length is no more than 5-7 words. By gradually increasing the length of sentences, you can bring their volume to 10–12 words. The same applies to the number of sentences and semantic chunks in the whole text.

So, short-term memory retains information received during the process of perception. Then the necessary part of the information enters long-term memory, where words, phrases and syntactic structures, rules and schemes for connecting them are stored. The volume of short-term memory can be increased with the help of special exercises. For example, “Listen to a series of words, phrases or sentences, repeat them,” “Listen to a sentence or series of sentences twice; determine what is missing or added.”

Understanding a text in both a native and a foreign language is associated with a transition from the external, expanded design of a thought to the abbreviated meaning of a statement. One can speak of a full understanding of the message only when the student is able to convey its main content in a few words. If a student understands all the words and phrases in the message he listened to, but cannot say what the meaning of what he listened to is, then the required level of understanding has not been achieved.

It is necessary to train students in paraphrasing sentences they hear, to develop their skills in equivalently replacing some words of the text with others in order to reduce the information received. To do this, you can use the following types of tasks: “Listen to the story and tell it briefly”; “Listen to the text and title it”; “From a number of given headings, select the most suitable one,” etc.

Difficulties in listening Learning to listen involves not only the development and training of speech mechanisms, but also the formation of skills to overcome difficulties associated with the conditions of perception and the characteristics of the semantic content and linguistic form of the message. Here are some of them: 1) the one-time presentation of information and the large volume of speech messages

significantly complicate the perception of the spoken text. Repeated listening improves understanding, promotes comprehension of new information, and its memorization.

The volume of the message is measured by the number of words (or listening time), at the initial stage - texts of a descriptive or narrative nature, consisting of 3-6 sentences (up to 2 minutes of playing time); 2) the speaker's fast speech rate, associated with rhythm, stress and pauses, interferes with successful listening (the average speech rate is 220–240 words per minute); 3) the subject content of the speech, depending on the age and interests of the listener, the plot and logic of constructing the sounding statement are also important for successful listening; 4) difficulties associated with the perception of the linguistic form of the message: phonetic, lexical, grammatical features of the spoken text.

The basic principles of constructing a system of exercises for teaching listening are determined by the nature of speech activity, the sequence of formation of the necessary skills and abilities to successfully overcome the listed difficulties. A system of exercises for teaching listening.

In the methodology of teaching listening, there are two types of exercises: a) training (preparatory) and b) communicative-speech. The purpose of the training exercises is to provide the technical side of listening, remove linguistic and psychological difficulties, and form listening mechanisms. These include: 1) exercises such as “Listen - repeat!”, “Listen - name!” for the development of phonemic hearing and the mechanism of internal pronunciation; 2) exercises related to breaking phrases into syntagms, substitution, transformation of intonation, and answering questions; 3) exercises for memorizing a series of words in a certain sequence, with grouping by meaning, expanding the structure and content, etc., aimed at developing the mechanism of RAM; 4) exercises to develop the mechanism for identifying concepts related to determining the meaning of words, finding a word in the specified meaning, and the ability to select synonyms and antonyms for it; 5) exercises for the formation of words belonging to other parts of speech (nouns from verbs), determining the meaning of new words by their elements; composing phrases; making assumptions about the content of the text based on the title, beginning, associated with the formation of a probabilistic forecasting mechanism and the development of linguistic guesswork, etc.

4) use perception guidelines (repetitions, pauses, rhetorical questions) when performing certain activities with a speech message; 5) understand the elements of subjective assessment; 6) retain factual material in memory; 84 7) distinguish between the influencing and pragmatic functions of speech messages, etc. The system of exercises when teaching listening should reflect the characteristics of this type of speech activity and take into account the sequence of formation of speech skills and abilities.

Conclusion. Thus, mastery of listening as a type of speech activity should ensure a successful communication process, develop students' ability to speak and understand a foreign language, and since this process is complex and difficult, schools need to pay more attention to this procedure. It is very important to increase students' motivation to understand foreign speech by ear. But there are all the prerequisites for improving the process of teaching listening: technology in modern times is developing at a high pace, and teachers have more and more opportunities to use various types of technical teaching aids.

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